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**EFFECT OF THREAD ON YARN QUALITY OF COTTON/POLYESTER
BLEND YARN**

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Enter. The strength, unevenness, hairiness of the blended yarn are improved by increasing the ratio of polyester fiber [1-2]. Processes such as carding, cleaning and blending increase the number of neps in cotton yarn [3]. The strength, unevenness, hairiness of the blended yarn depends on the fiber properties, the ratio in the blend, the spindle speed of the spinning machine [4], the yarn count, the high roller pressure and the twist coefficient of the drafting pairs [5-6]. When spinning high quality yarns, the influence of the diameter of the draw rolls, the initial elongation and the twist coefficient imparted to the web on the tensile force in the draw zone has been studied [7-8]. The breakage of the fiber in the thread is determined by the core strength of the fiber and the correct distribution of the fibers along the length of the thread [9].

Test methods. The experimental work was carried out in the scientific laboratory of the "Spinning Department" of TTYeSI, and 14.7-tex cotton/polyester 80/20% blend yarns were spun by the ring spinning process with 850, 918 and 988 twists in three different samples manufactured. Quality parameters of mixed yarns Unevenness indicators of mixed yarns in the conditions of the quality laboratory near the company "BAKAN TEX" Tests for 3000m of yarns at a speed of 400m/min on Uster® Tester 6 and mechanical indicators of Uster® Tensojet 4 devices are made 3 times repeated, the results are averaged.

The purpose of the research work. The aim was to develop new ranges of raw materials and increase the quality level of the ranges in the manufacture of outerwear products for weaving from a mixture of cotton and polyester fibers. For this purpose, the influence of the twists given when spinning cotton/polyester 80/20% blend yarn on the quality parameters of the finished yarn was studied. Cotton fibers of the "Sultan" selection variety and polyester fibers were used to produce mixed yarn samples.

The result analysis. Figure 1. When 850 twists were given to the yarn spun from 80/20% polyester/polyester mixture, the thin areas of the yarn (Figure 2 a) recorded an index of 58 [t/km]. When 918 twists are given, the thin areas of the thread increase by 12%, and we can see that the coefficient of variation according to b) decreases by 42.93%. When we gave 988 twists to the mixed yarn, the thinnest areas of the yarn a) and their coefficients of variation b) recorded the highest index.

Figure 2. Thin areas of cotton/polyester blend yarns a) and their coefficients of variation b)

In Fig 3, when we give 850 to 918 twists to the cotton/polyester mixed yarn, the yarn a) the specific tensile strength by 11,36% and the coefficient of variation according to b), improvement by 12,27% was observed. The tensile strength of twists 988 mixed yarn was the lowest and the coefficient of variation was the highest.

Figure 3. Cotton/polyester blend yarn a) comparison cut off tenacity and b) coefficient of variation

a)

b)

Figure 4. Hairiness of cotton/polyester blend yarns a) and their coefficient of variation b)

In the process of spinning cotton/polyester 80/20% mixed yarn , when we give 850 and 918 twist to yarns, in figure 4 a) hairiness indicator λ from 5.47 to 4.91 or by 10.23 % decreased we will see can a mix of threads twist increase with hairiness of threads coefficients of variation according to b) increased went.

Conclusion. Education for intended cotton/polyester 80/20% blend of yarn twist from 850 to 918 when we increase of yarn uneven, thin by mass and thick places, the number increased if their coefficients of variation and hairiness level declined. A mix of yarn maturity according to when twist 918 is given of threads of tensile strength, tensile strength and work of break indicators increase was determined. When twist 988 is given while mixed of yarn irregularities increase , ripeness decreased yarn quality and it got worse . Weaving for intended cotton/polyester 80/20% blend yarn in spinning twist conclusion that the optimal option is 918 turns/meter to do can.

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